

Synthesis of Nanoparticles from Papaya Leaf Extract

**Aindra Prana Gotama^{1)*}, I Gusti Ngurah Agung Adi Primantara¹⁾, I Ketut Cahyadi
Adi Winata Sutarta¹⁾, Ni Luh Made Wina Putri Maharani¹⁾, Shella Greatya Noke¹⁾.**

¹Fakultas Kedokteran dan Ilmu Kesehatan Universitas Warmadewa, Jl. Akasia XVI A No.1, Panjer, Kec.

Denpasar Tim., Kota Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia

*Penulis Korespondensi : aindrpranagotama@gmail.com

Abstract

In 2020, the cancer incidence rate reached 19,292,789, while the number of cancer-related deaths was 9,958,133 worldwide (Sung et al., 2021). [1] Over the past five years, the prevalence of cancer in Indonesia has increased from 1.4% to 1.49%. Various cancer therapies have been implemented, one of which is chemotherapy, which works by inhibiting cell proliferation to kill cancer cells. However, chemotherapy is less selective in targeting cancer cells, leading to significant side effects for patients. Therefore, researchers aim to develop alternative therapies using plants, one of which is papaya leaves. Carica papaya Linn., or papaya, belongs to the Caricaceae family, originating from Central America and southern Mexico, and is commonly grown in India. It has been used for its medicinal properties worldwide. Papaya plants are typically unbranched, with smooth stems and long-petioled leaves that have five to six lobes. Anticancer agents are compounds used in cancer therapy. The classes of compounds responsible for anticancer mechanisms include phenolics, flavonoids, phytosterols, carotenoids, ascorbic acid, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and pheophorbide A. The stages of this research include extraction, nanoparticle synthesis, encapsulation, characterization, and analysis.

Keywords: cancer, nanoparticles, and papaya leaves

INTRODUCTION

In 2020, the global cancer incidence rate reached 19,292,789, while the number of cancer-related deaths was 9,958,133 [1]. Over the past five years, the prevalence of cancer in Indonesia has increased from 1.4% to 1.49%. Cancer is a disease caused by uncontrolled growth and spread of abnormal cells to other parts of the body. It can result from dietary patterns, lifestyle choices, excessive alcohol consumption, and exposure to carcinogenic substances. The pathogenesis of cancer generally involves the mediation of oncogene activity and the inactivation of tumor suppressor genes. Various cancer therapies have been implemented, including chemotherapy, which kills cancer cells by inhibiting cell proliferation. However, chemotherapy is less selective in targeting cancer cells, leading to significant side effects for patients. Therefore, researchers aim to develop alternative therapies using plants, one of which is papaya leaves [2].

METHOD

Equipment and Material

This research employs several equipment and materials. The tools used in this study include a Particle Size Analyzer (PSA), a Homogenizer (Biologics Inc 300 V/T), a set of maceration tools, an Evaporator (Heidolph), a spray dryer, analytical balances (Ohaus and Mettler Toledo), a climatic Chamber (Memmert), transmission electron microscopy, a refrigerator (Sharp), volumetric flasks, beakers, graduated cylinders, micropipettes, vials, dropper pipettes, and general glassware commonly found in laboratories. The materials used in this research are papaya leaves, 70% ethanol, chitosan, and sodium tripolyphosphate.

Extraction Stage

The extraction process is carried out through two steps: maceration and reflux, aimed at obtaining optimal extraction of papaya leaves. In this section, the techniques used include analysis of yield, antioxidant activity, and total phenolic compounds.

Nanoparticle Synthesis Stage

A concentration of 100 ppm was prepared by weighing 5 grams of papaya leaf extract and then mixing it with 12.5 mL of AgNO₃ solution and 3.75 mL of distilled water. This mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 30 minutes. Next, a concentration of 150 ppm was prepared by weighing 7.5 grams of papaya leaf extract and mixing it with 18.7 mL of AgNO₃ solution and 31.3 mL of distilled water. For a concentration of 200 ppm, 10 grams of papaya leaf extract were mixed with 25 mL of AgNO₃ solution and 25 mL of distilled water. After preparation, particle size characterization was performed using a Particle Size Analyzer (PSA) with UV-Vis method [3,4].

Analysis Stages

Analysis of Antioxidant Activity
Using the DPPH Method

RESULT

Phytochemical Test and Antioxidant Test

This analysis aims to determine the presence of metabolites in papaya leaf extract through color tests with various reagents. The results of the qualitative phytochemical analysis are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Phytochemical Screening and Antioxidant Screening Results

No.	Golongan Kimia	Hasil
1	Alkaloid	-/Negatif
2	Flavonoid	+/Positif
3	Tanin	+/Positif
4	Fenol	+/Positif
5	Steroid	+/Positif
6	Terpenoid	+/Positif
7	Saponin	+/Positif
8	Antioksidan (IC50)	168,31 ppm

Nanoparticle Test

The nanoparticle testing results indicate that the silver nanoparticles obtained from papaya leaf extract have a particle size of 99.01 nm at a concentration of 100 ppm, 96.75 nm at a

concentration of 150 ppm, and 82.63 nm at a concentration of 200 ppm.

DISCUSSION

In the qualitative phytochemical test, it was found that papaya leaf extract contains flavonoids, tannins, and steroids, as shown in Table 1. The chemical compounds identified in papaya leaves include alkaloids, phenols, saponins, flavonoids, and tannins [5]. These differences are attributed to environmental factors such as climate, sunlight, air temperature, and soil water availability. In nanoparticle testing, it was observed that as the concentration increases, the particle size decreases. This result indicates that the particle sizes obtained are within the acceptable range, as particles less than 300 nm are ideal for use in drug delivery systems.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion obtained from this paper is that papaya leaf extract through qualitative phytochemical tests contains flavonoid, tannin, and steroid compounds. The group of compounds responsible for anticancer mechanisms are phenolics, flavonoids, phytosterols, carotene, ascorbic acid, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and pheophirbide A. The results of nanoparticle testing showed good results in drug delivery so that it can be used as the right formulation in making anticancer nanoparticles.

THANK YOU NOTE

Aindra Prana Gotama, I Gusti Ngurah Agung Adi Primantara, I Ketut Cahyadi Adi Winata Sutarta, Ni Luh Made Wina Putri Maharani, Shella Greatya Noke Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universitas Warmadewa (FKIK Unwar), prepared this journal article based on the report from the pharmaceutical research journal on the potential of papaya leaves

as an anticancer. This work was funded by FKIK Unwar through the 2023 Faculty Grant Student Research Activity. The opinions expressed herein are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of funding agency.

REFERENCES

1. Sung, H., et al. (2021). 'Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries'. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians* 71(3): 209–249
2. Rahmawati, A. M., Anam, K., & Sasikirana, W. (2023). Review Artikel: Potensi Daun Pepaya (*Carica papaya L.*) sebagai Antikanker. *Generics: Journal of Research in Pharmacy* 3(1): 27-35
3. Putri, N.M.M.S., Sutiningsih, D. and Hadi, N.M. (2023). Skrining Fitokimia Dan Uji Antibakteri Nanopartikel Perak Ekstrak Daun Pepaya (*Carica Papaya L*) Terhadap Bakteri *Staphylococcus Epidermidis* Dan *Salmonella Typhi*. *Jurnal Bios Logos*, 13(3), pp.141–149. doi:<https://doi.org/10.35799/jbl.v13i3.49813>.
4. Banala, R.R., Nagati, V.B. and Karnati, P.R. (2015). Green Synthesis and Characterization of *Carica Papaya* Leaf Extract Coated Silver Nanoparticles through X-ray diffraction, Electron Microscopy and Evaluation of Bactericidal Properties. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 22(5), pp.637–644. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2015.01.007>.
5. Alzanando R, Yusuf M, Tutik T. Analisis Kadar Senyawa Alkaloid dan Flavonoid Total Ekstrak Etanol Daun Pepaya (*Carica papaya L.*) Menggunakan Spektrofotometri UV-Vis. *Jurnal Farmasi Malahayati*. 14;5(1):108–20. doi:<https://doi.org/10.33024/jfm.v5i1.7032>